

1 *Devyāmata* chapter 77: the positions of the deities in the body of the site (vāstudeha) edition

vāstudehe devatāsthānirdeśasaptasaptatimapāṭalaḥ, edition.

N f79v, line 4; M f46v, line 3; W f50v, line 1.

77.1 vāstuno 'vayavāvasthaṃ vāstudevān pṛthak pṛthak
kathayāmi viśeṣeṇa saṃkṣepān na vistarāt

77.2 vāstudehasthitān devān vāstuno 'vayavān śṛṇu
īśānyāṃ tu śiras tasya pāḍau niritigocare

77.3 dakṣiṇaṃ kurparaṃ jānur āgneyyāṃ saṃvyavasthitam
vāmakurparaṃ jānuś ca vāyavyāṃ saṃvyavasthitam

77.4 īśānaḥ śirasi jñeyaḥ sarvalokādhipaprabhuḥ
parjanya ditināmā ca dakṣiṇavāmanetrayoḥ

77.5 jayantaś cāditīś caiva karṇayor ubhayoḥ sthitau
mukhe āpaḥ sthito jñeya āpavatso gale sthitaḥ

N f80r

77.6 stanayoḥ pūrvavaj jñeyau āryamaṃpṛthivīdharau
mahendraś ca tathānanta urasi saṃvyavasthitau

77.7 hṛdaye hastayor brahmā ādityo dakṣiṇe bhujē
vāmabhujē tathā somo bāhusthāne 'marāñ chrṇu

Ω = NM(→W)

3cd is missing at N.

At M, the folio that carries 77.7a – 78.10 is misplaced in the stack. W, in copying M, maintains this disordered account. I have not been able to locate 77.7a – 78.10 in W.

1b devān] em.; devā NM 1c viśeṣeṇa] N; śeṣeṇa M 1d saṃkṣepān] N; saṃksepā M
2b vāstuno 'vayavān] N; vāstunovayavā M • śṛṇu] N; śṛṇuḥ M 2d niriti] N; nairiti M
4a īśānaḥ] N; īśāna M • śirasi] N; śiriṣi M • jñeyaḥ] N; jñeyas M
4b lokādhipa] em.; lokādhipaḥ NM 4d dakṣiṇa] em.; dakṣiṇo N; dakṣiṇā M
5b ubhayoḥ] em.; ubhayo NM 5c āpaḥ] em.; āpa NM 5d āpavatso] N; āpavatsā M
• gale] M; [**] N • sthitaḥ] N; sthitā M 6a pūrvavaj] M; pūrva N • jñeyau] N; jñeyo M
6b pṛthivī] N; pṛthavī M 7a hṛdaye] N; hṛdayo M
7b ādityo dakṣiṇe] em.; ādityodiṇe M; [*****] N 7d 'marāñ] em.; marāc NM

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- 77.8 satyo bhr̥śāambarau cāgniḥ pūṣā ca dakṣiṇe 'marāḥ
daurdaṇḍe dakṣiṇe proktā vāme ca śṛṇu sāmpratam
- 77.9 bhalvāṭo mukhyanāgau ca tathā rogaś caturthakaḥ
pañcamo pāpayakṣmā ca bāhudaṇḍe tu paścime
- 77.10 sāvitrī savitā caiva kalikāyāṃ krameṇa tu
rudraś ca rājayakṣmā ca kalikāyāṃ tathottare
- 77.11 pārśve tu dakṣiṇe jñeyo vitathaś ca gṛhakṣataḥ
vāme śoṣāsaurau jñeyau ūruke dakṣiṇe yamaḥ
- 77.12 vāme ca varuṇo deva ūruke paścime sthitaḥ
vivasvā ca tathā mitro dvāv etau jaṭharasthitau
- 77.13 indrarāgo jayopendro vṛṣaṇe ca vyavasthitaḥ
vāstudevānyathāvastham jaṅghayoḥ śṛṇu sāmpratam
- 77.14 gandharvo bhr̥ṅgarājaś ca mṛgaś caiva tathāparaḥ
jaṅghāyāṃ dakṣiṇāyāṃ tu trayo devā vyavasthitāḥ

Ω = NM(→W)

- 8a satyo] N; satyau M • bhr̥śāambarau] em.; bṛśāambarau NM • cāgniḥ] em.; cāgni NM
8b pūṣā] em.; puṣpa NM 8c daur] N; do M 9a bhalvāṭo] em.; bhalvāṭa NM
10a sāvitrī] em.; sāvitr̥ N; sāvitrī M 10b kalikāyāṃ] N; kalpīvāyā M
10c rudraś] em.; rudraś NM 10c kalikāyāṃ] conj.; kaliyikā NM
• tathottare] N; tuthottare M 11a jñeyo] em.; jñeyā NM
11c śoṣāsaurau] em.; soṣāsaurau N; seṣausvarau M 12b sthitaḥ] N; sthit[[o]]aḥ M
12c vivasvā] M; vivasvāś N 12d sthitau] N; sthitauḥ M 13a rāgo] N; nāgo M
• jayopendra] M; jayomendra N 13c stham] N; sthām M
14a bhr̥ṅga] M; bṛṅga N 14c jaṅghāyāṃ] N; jaṅghāyā M
• dakṣiṇāyāṃ] N; dakṣiṇeyāṃ M

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77.15 puṣpadantaś ca sugrīvas tathā dvauvāriko 'paraḥ
vāstuno vāmajaṅghasthāḥ pādayoḥ pitarah sthitāḥ

77.16 vāstudevāḥ samākhyātā vāstudehe yathāsthitāḥ
abhidhānaṃ tu tat teṣāṃ procyate śṛṇu sāmpratam

iti vāstudehe devatāsthānanirdeśasaptasaptatimapāṭalaḥ

$\Omega = NM(\rightarrow W)$

15d pitarah] N; pitara M 16a devāḥ] em.; devā NM

after 16 iti vāstudehe devatāsthānanirdeśasaptasaptatimapāṭalaḥ] em.;

itivāstudehedeivatāsthānanirdeśapaṭalaḥ N;

itidevyāmatevāstudehedeivatāsthānanirdeśasaptasaptatimapāṭalaḥ M